

Paper proposal

«It's time to recognise that “brotherly peoples” are simply neighbours ». Lesya Ukrainka and the differentiation of borders

Lesya Ukrainka (1871-1913, real name Laryssa Kossatch-Kvitka) called herself after the name her country wanted to choose for itself. Rus', Ruthenia, Little Russia, Ukraine: these names question the conception of Ukrainian identity/of Ukraine's borders. The question of borders is therefore central to Ukrainka's reflection on Ukrainian cultural identity.

My paper will develop along three lines:

- 1) *Experiences of borders*. For Ukrainka, the border is a fact of experience. Her family had experience of exile: exile occurs when the borders of a territory that is perceived both by the subject and the authorities as familiar are forcibly crossed and cannot be crossed again in the other direction. Paradoxically, exile within the Russian Empire weakens the borders by creating cross-border movements, but in the same time strengthens their perception through the very idea of exile. Ukrainka also experienced borders when, following on from the oukazes of Ems and Valuev, her books were prevented from leaving the Empire for Europe. For her, this turned the *granitsa* (border) into a penitentiary wall, with the laws using the principle of *ogranitchenia* (limitation) to preserve the Empire frightened by danger coming from abroad (*iz raganitsi*, literally, from beyond the border) or circulating from the non-Russian peripheries of the Empire to abroad.
- 2) *Eastern/Western borders*. For Ukrainka, crossing the western border of Ukraine meant opening up a field of cultural possibilities which, on the other side of the other border (the eastern one) became a field of impossibilities. It meant finding oneself in a space from which Ukrainian independence could be imagined: Ukrainka wrote to her brother in Vienna on 25.02.1891 that she had never « felt as concretely » as « on that side » of the border « how heavy the [Russian imperialist] chains are ». For her, in the West, the border separates what Ukraine would like to be (a cultural space like Galicia) from what it is (a periphery of the Russian Empire). In the East, it separates Ukraine from what it does not want to be (the Russian Empire in the form of one of its peripheries).
- 3) *Internal/external borders*. In 1840, Custine wrote that Russia was « a prison made all the more formidable by the fact that its limits are more difficult to reach and cross ». But these were the outer limits. The Empire's internal borders were of a different nature. From an imperialist point of view, the Russian Empire was a kind of Russian doll, a nest of territories where the *idem* linking the peoples was more important than the *ipse* differentiating them. Despite the peripheral etymology of the word Ukraine (*krai* would mean the limit, the frontier), Ukrainka has chosen to claim to be “Ukrainian”, in reaction to the appellation Little Russia, which inscribes Ukraine into an imaginary Russian trinitarian brotherhood (Little/White/Great Russia). For her, it was vital that the borders regain all their symbolic significance: « It's time to recognise that “brotherly peoples” are simply neighbours », she wrote in a letter dated 03.03.1903.

Biobibliographical note

Nikol Dziub is a Swiss National Science Foundation Postdoctoral Fellow at the University of Basel (Chair of East European History) for a research project devoted to Lesya Ukrainka and her posterity in the USSR and post-1991 Ukraine. She holds two Masters degrees (Taras Chevtchenko University, Kyiv, Ukraine; Ecole Normale Supérieure, Lyon, France) and a doctorate in French, general and comparative literature (Université de Haute-Alsace, France, 2015). She has published two essays (*Voyages en Andalousie au XIX^e siècle. La Fabrique de la modernité romantique* [Journées through Andalusia in the 19th Century. The Creation of Romantic Modernity], Droz, 2018; “*Son arme était la harpe*”. *Pouvoirs de la femme et du barde chez Nizami et dans Le Livre de Dede Korkut* [“Her Weapon was the Harp.” *The Power of Women and Bards in Nizami’s Works and in The Book of Dede Korkut*], LitVerlag, 2018), edited the correspondence between André Gide and the Petersburg Orientalist of German-Baltic origin Fédor Rosenberg (Presses universitaires de Lyon, 2021, as part of a postdoctoral project on André Gide and the USSR funded by the « Catherine Gide Foundation and Fondation des Treilles Prize »), and co-translated Lina Kostenko’s *Journal d’un fou ukrainien* ([*Diary of a Ukrainian Madman*], L’Harmattan, 2022). A specialist in travel literature, women’s writing, the relationship between literature and imperialism, and representations/constructions of liminal and peripheral spaces, she has edited a dozen collective volumes and published some sixty articles, including (in relation to the subject of her proposal):

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- Dziub, N. (2017) “Ligne de vie ou tracé de mort? La frontière dans la littérature ukrainienne” [“Lifeline or Lethal Layout? The Boundary in Ukrainian Literature”], *Adhoc Journal*, No. 5: “La Frontière” [“The Boundary”], <https://adhoc.hypotheses.org/ad-hoc-n5-la-frontiere-resumes-des-articles/nikol-dziub-ligne-de-vie-ou-trace-de-mort-la-frontiere-dans-la-litterature-ukrainienne>